

A responsible AI-driven framework for robust and transparent software vulnerability detection

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ABSTRACT

Context: Software vulnerability detection (SVD) is increasingly challenged by the scale and complexity of modern software systems. Although deep learning and LLM-based approaches demonstrate strong detection performance, their adoption in security-critical settings is limited by insufficient interpretability, adversarial resilience, and systematic Responsible AI integration.

Objective: This paper aims to design and evaluate a Responsible AI-driven framework for SVD that operationalizes fairness, interpretability, security, reliability, and transparency without compromising detection effectiveness.

Method: We propose a model-agnostic vulnerability detection framework that incorporates fairness-aware data preprocessing, multi-model evaluation, and structured verification mechanisms. Interpretability is achieved through multi-view explanations combining global and local SHAP, LIME, and attention-based attribution. Explanation consistency is examined using attention-guided token occlusion, while security is evaluated via multiple white-box adversarial attacks on correctly classified test samples. The framework is validated on three public datasets — CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul — using deep learning and pre-trained LLMs.

Results: Experimental results demonstrate competitive detection performance across datasets while providing structured explanation and adversarial evaluation evidence. Interpretability analyses reveal dataset-specific vulnerability cues aligned with domain knowledge, and perturbation studies show consistent confidence shifts under controlled token masking. Adversarial experiments further illustrate stable performance trends under attack conditions.

Conclusion: The findings indicate that Responsible AI principles can be systematically operationalized within deep learning and LLM-based SVD pipelines. By integrating fairness, interpretability, security evaluation, reliability assessment, and transparency mechanisms, the proposed framework supports trustworthy and security-aware deployment of AI-driven vulnerability detection systems.

1. Introduction

The increasing complexity and scale of modern software systems have led to a persistent growth in software vulnerabilities, posing serious risks to security, reliability, and trustworthiness. Rapid development cycles, feature-driven releases, and the widespread adoption of open-source software often prioritize functionality over rigorous security assurance, leaving systems exposed to exploitable flaws [1].

Recent vulnerability trends underscore the growing scale of the problem. The 2026 Vulnerability Forecast by the Forum of Incident Response and Security Teams (FIRST) projects that annual Common

Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs) will exceed 50,000 for the first time, with a median estimate of approximately 59,000 disclosures in 2026 [2]. This sustained growth in reported vulnerabilities significantly increases analysis and remediation workload, reinforcing the need for scalable, reliable, and trustworthy AI-driven software vulnerability detection systems.

Traditional vulnerability detection techniques, including static analysis, dynamic testing, penetration testing, and manual code audits, remain foundational in software security practice. However, these methods are time-consuming, labor-intensive, and increasingly inadequate

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for handling large-scale codebases and rapidly evolving threat landscapes [3]. As a result, automated and learning-based approaches have gained significant attention as scalable alternatives.

Recent advances in deep learning and large language models (LLMs) have enabled automated vulnerability detection by learning patterns directly from source code and program representations [4–6]. Deep neural models and LLMs can analyze raw code tokens, control-flow information, and contextual semantics to identify vulnerabilities earlier in the software development lifecycle. Despite their promising performance, deep learning and LLMs introduce critical challenges that hinder their adoption in security-critical settings. First, their inherently opaque nature limits interpretability, making it difficult for developers and security analysts to understand why a specific code fragment is classified as vulnerable [7,8]. Second, these models are highly sensitive to data quality and class imbalance, which can introduce biases and unfair detection behavior across different vulnerability types or projects [9]. Third, deep learning and LLMs are vulnerable to adversarial manipulation, where small, carefully crafted perturbations can significantly alter detections, undermining robustness and trust [10, 11].

These limitations highlight the necessity of integrating *Responsible AI* principles into vulnerability detection systems. Responsible AI emphasizes fairness, interpretability, transparency, reliability, and security across the entire model lifecycle [12]. While prior work has explored individual aspects such as interpretability or robustness in isolation, the systematic incorporation of Responsible AI principles into deep learning and LLM-based vulnerability detection pipelines remains limited [13]. In particular, existing approaches rarely validate whether explanations are faithful to model decisions, whether detections remain reliable under adversarial conditions, or whether fairness considerations are addressed during data preparation and training.

To bridge this gap, this paper proposes a Responsible AI-driven vulnerability detection framework that embeds ethical and trust-oriented mechanisms directly into the detection pipeline. Rather than treating Responsible AI as a post-hoc add-on, our approach integrates fairness-aware data balancing, multi-view interpretability, faithfulness validation, and adversarial robustness evaluation as first-class components of the system. We empirically evaluate the framework across multiple vulnerability datasets, including CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul, using a diverse set of deep learning and pre-trained LLMs.

This study is guided by the following research questions.

RQ1: How can Responsible AI principles — fairness, interpretability, security, reliability, and transparency — be systematically operationalized within a deep learning and LLM-based software vulnerability detection pipeline across data preparation, model training, and evaluation stages?

RQ2: To what extent do interpretability mechanisms provide reliable and decision-consistent explanations for vulnerability detections across different datasets?

RQ3: How secure and reliable are the proposed vulnerability detection models when evaluated under adversarial perturbations compared to clean inference conditions?

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- We propose a unified Responsible AI-driven framework for software vulnerability detection that operationalizes fairness, interpretability, security, reliability, and transparency across data preparation, model training, and evaluation within a structured pipeline.
- We introduce a multi-view interpretability strategy combining SHAP (local and global), LIME, attention rollout, and token occlusion to provide instance-level and dataset-level explanations, along with validation of explanation consistency through controlled perturbation analysis.
- We evaluate security and reliability under adversarial conditions using multiple white-box attacks on a correct-only test subset, providing empirical evidence of model behavior beyond clean inference.

- We conduct extensive experiments on CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul datasets, demonstrating consistent performance trends while providing structured assurance evidence to support transparent and trustworthy vulnerability detection.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses the related work based on the challenges of Responsible AI. Section 3 provides an overview of Responsible AI. In Section 4, we provide the complete details about the proposed approach. Section 5 provides the experimental setup and results of the proposed approach. Section 6 discusses threats to validity, and Section 7 concludes this work with future work (see Table 1).

2. Literature review

This literature review explores critical aspects influencing software vulnerability detection using machine learning and deep learning. It is organized into four subsections: (i) Adoption of deep learning and LLMs for vulnerability detection, examining how various models have been applied to detect software vulnerabilities; (ii) Availability of Quality Datasets, addressing the importance of reliable data sources for training robust models; (iii) Training with Quality Data, discussing the impact of data quality on model performance and fairness; and (iv) Challenges of Interpreting Deep Learning Models, identifying existing difficulties in understanding and explaining model decisions. Together, these subsections provide a comprehensive overview of the foundational elements and current gaps addressed in this study.

2.1. Adoption of deep learning and llms for vulnerability detection

Vulnerability detection in software systems is a crucial aspect of cybersecurity. The application of deep learning and LLMs to this domain has attracted significant attention in recent years due to their potential to revolutionize traditional approaches. Dong et al. [6] introduced DeKeDVer, a versatile vulnerability classifier that improves classification by incorporating both vulnerability descriptions and source code information. Their methodology preprocesses vulnerability descriptions, selects relevant text features, and applies a Text Recurrent Convolutional Neural Network (TextRCNN) to effectively understand textual information. Additionally, DeKeDVer utilizes the Code Property Graph (CPG) from source code, extracting essential domains and embedding them. These feature vectors from both vulnerability descriptions and source code are then combined using the Relational Graph Attention Network (RGAT), with a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) layer finalizing the classification process. Three different ML models, Linear Regression (LR), Decision Tree (DT), and Random Forest (RF) are considered to predicate vulnerability exploitation in the healthcare context by [16]. The work makes use of ontology which provides the formal specification and description of the healthcare ecosystem and key concepts of vulnerability assessment. The experiment part considers the CVSS dataset for detection with 63% accuracy. Chang et al. [4] proposed the VDDA model, an innovative approach to software vulnerability detection that combines deep learning with attention mechanisms to forego traditional feature engineering. The model preprocesses source code using the Joren slice tool and optimizes code attribute graphs (CPG) before applying deep learning models. The integration of an attention mechanism significantly enhances both the accuracy and efficiency of vulnerability detection, with experimental results demonstrating superior performance compared to existing methods. Tian et al. [5] introduced S2FVD, an innovative tool that adopts a multifaceted approach to vulnerability detection. S2FVD analyzes software code from multiple perspectives, including token sequences, attributed control flow graphs (ACFG), and abstract syntax trees (AST), extracting features indicative of vulnerabilities for a more comprehensive codebase understanding.

Deep learning models, utilizing algorithms such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), have

Table 1
Comparison of representative software vulnerability detection approaches.

Work	Model	Dataset	Core idea	Performance	Responsible AI gaps
Dong et al. (2023) [6]	DeKeDVer	NVD (C/C++)	Combines vulnerability descriptions with source code features for classification	F1 = 84.5%	Interpretability, transparency
Chang et al. (2023) [4]	VDDA	NVD, SARD	Attention-based deep learning without manual feature engineering	F1 = 96.3%	Fairness, transparency
Tian et al. (2023) [5]	S2FVD	D2A	Multi-representation fusion (tokens, CFG, AST)	F1 = 98.1%	Interpretability, fairness
An et al. (2023) [7]	V-CNN	MITRE CVE/CWE	CNN-based vulnerability detection outperforming classical methods	Acc = 98%	Security, transparency
Zafra et al. (2023) [13] Rossini et al. (2022) [14]	CNN, LSTM	SySeVR; SmartBugs	Smart contract vulnerability detection using DL	Acc = 99%; F1 = 83.8%	Fairness, transparency
Yuan et al. (2023) [15]	VulBG	FFMpeg, Chrome	Behavior-graph modeling of inter-function relations	F1 = 56.1%	Reliability, fairness, interpretability

been extensively applied for the automatic detection of potential bugs and vulnerabilities in software systems. An et al. [17] developed a model called V-CNN, which uses CNN algorithms to detect CWE/CVE vulnerabilities. Yuan et al. [15] addressed deep learning-based vulnerability detection systems' limitations, proposing a novel framework called VulBG that leverages a Behavior Graph Model to extract and capture function behaviors and their relationships. Rossini et al. [14] explored the use of CNNs and LSTM networks for identifying and classifying smart contract vulnerabilities, confirming the high accuracy and potential of deep learning methods in this domain. RNNs, known for their sequence detection capabilities, along with their variations such as RNN-Transducers (RNN-Ts), Gated Recurrence Units (GRUs), and Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) cells, have shown promise in various applications, addressing challenges like vanishing gradients [18] [19, 20]. The Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP), a fundamental deep learning component, has seen widespread use across different problems, with recent advancements revealing its hidden potential for performance improvement [21,21]. MLP models have also been extended to image generation tasks using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), showing superiority over pure CNN networks in small datasets [22]. In the domain of millimeter wave (MMW) communication, a deep learning method named MLP-mmWP has been proposed for localization, achieving better performance than existing methods [23]. Beyond traditional deep learning architectures, recent vulnerability detection studies have also started to examine LLM-based methods. Zheng et al. [8] referenced baselines built on RoBERTa, CodeBERT, and GraphCodeBERT, reflecting the growing adoption of pretrained transformer models in this area.

2.2. Availability of quality dataset

Deep learning and LLMs have achieved significant progress in software vulnerability detection; however, they must address practical challenges such as class imbalance and cross-type generalization. Class imbalance arises when non-vulnerable code substantially outnumbers vulnerable instances, which can bias model learning and evaluation. Additionally, large-scale vulnerability corpora often contain heterogeneous weakness categories and diverse coding patterns, increasing the difficulty of consistent generalization across vulnerability types. The DiverseVul dataset [24] exemplifies such large-scale and heterogeneous settings, encompassing a broad range of CWEs and substantial variability in code structure. Rather than representing a limitation, this diversity provides a valuable testbed for evaluating model robustness and generalization behavior under realistic and complex conditions. By including DiverseVul alongside CWE-119 and CWE-399, this study assesses the proposed framework across both focused and heterogeneous vulnerability distributions.

In a recent study, Steenhoek et al. [25] broadened their perspective by studying how the size of training data, coupled with the diversity of the projects in the Devign and MSR datasets, affects vulnerability detection model performance. This paper will, therefore, seek to understand how increasing the size of a dataset and collecting a more comprehensive range of projects may affect the accuracy and efficiency of vulnerability detection efforts. Furthermore, another paper by Yuan et al. [15] evaluated the ability of VulBG to find vulnerabilities in real-world data collection. Their results show that VulBG significantly improves baseline model performance when detecting vulnerabilities in balanced and unbalanced datasets. The results of the models indicate that VulBG has the potential capability to improve accurate vulnerability detection; therefore, it can help enhance the overall security of the system. SySeVR framework [26] was introduced for vulnerability detection research using the SeVC dataset from the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) and Software Assurance Reference Dataset (SARD). SySeVR targets a broader approach to vulnerability discovery for C/C++ projects by assessing vulnerabilities based on syntax and semantics. Another critical source would be the Software Assurance Reference Dataset (SARD) [27], where their host is the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). SARD enhances the precision of those tools that can determine source code vulnerabilities.

2.3. Training with quality data

Data quality issues, such as data duplication and unrealistic distributions of vulnerable classes, significantly undermine the effectiveness of models designed for automated software vulnerability detection. These problems can lead models to learn irrelevant artifacts rather than the critical features that indicate software vulnerabilities. Software vulnerability datasets frequently contain inaccuracies in vulnerability labels and have a high level of data duplication. Many datasets have incorrect vulnerability labels and numerous duplicate data points, which can distort the training process and hinder the model's ability to generalize to real-world situations [28]. This then makes the training of effective models a complex task since false benchmark performance is falsely inflated by a false perception of model predictive power [29]. Indeed, the paramount need to improve software vulnerability data quality assessment and consideration in light of existing challenges would then be requisite. To clean the data and improve the reliability of the automated software vulnerability detection system, we propose cautious data cleaning, adjustment of the data distribution, and bettering label accuracy. This would increase their overall trustworthiness and usefulness manyfold, such that we can use them more effectively for the detection of actual vulnerabilities and the improvement of software systems' security. These are the critical steps taken, not only from a

technical point of view but also to build confidence in AI-based security measures. On the importance in that view, the role of the importance of practice in Data Quality Management is continuously advancing [30].

2.4. Challenges of interpreting deep learning and llms detection

Despite their strong predictive capabilities, deep learning models are often criticized for operating as “black boxes”, making their decision processes difficult to interpret. This lack of transparency poses challenges in security-critical domains such as software vulnerability detection, where understanding the rationale behind a flagged vulnerability is essential for trust and practical adoption. To address this limitation, model-agnostic explanation techniques such as LIME and SHAP are widely used to provide local and global interpretability [31]. These methods attribute importance scores to input features, enabling analysts to identify which tokens or code patterns influence model detections. Das et al. [32] further propose AuthSHAP, a robust SHAP-based framework designed to expose latent weaknesses in machine-learning systems by highlighting influential yet underutilized features. In high-security contexts, interpretability must also be accompanied by reliability and stability assessment. Sotgiu et al. [33] emphasize structured evaluation of transformer-based vulnerability detection models, demonstrating how SHAP-based analyses can reveal feature relevance and support systematic inspection of model behavior. Such approaches contribute not only to explainability but also to debugging, robustness analysis, and informed model comparison across datasets.

3. An overview of responsible AI

Responsible AI is an approach that embeds ethical, accountability, and governance considerations into the design, development, and deployment of AI systems. Its goal is to ensure that AI systems are not only effective, but also trustworthy and aligned with societal values. In this study, Responsible AI is operationalized through five core assurance dimensions: (i) *fairness*, (ii) *interpretability*, (iii) *security*, (iv) *reliability*, and (v) *transparency* [34].

In the context of software vulnerability detection (SVD), these dimensions are particularly critical because model detections directly influence security triage and remediation decisions. Misclassifications may lead to missed vulnerabilities (false negatives) or unnecessary remediation effort (false positives), thereby affecting both system safety and developer productivity. Accordingly, we treat these Responsible AI dimensions as operational assurance targets that are evaluated through concrete practices across the model lifecycle, including data preparation, model training and selection, and post-training verification.

Fairness: Fairness refers to minimizing systematic bias in model behavior and ensuring that the learning process does not favor one class or subgroup due to skewed data or spurious correlations. In vulnerability detection, fairness is operationalized primarily as bias-aware learning conditions where vulnerable and non-vulnerable classes are not disproportionately represented during training, thereby reducing a tendency to over-predict the majority class. Fairness assurance therefore includes careful dataset preparation, explicit reporting of class distributions, and evaluation procedures that reduce biased decision boundaries [35].

Interpretability: Interpretability is the extent to which an AI system can provide human-understandable explanations for its detections. It enables developers and security analysts to inspect the evidence behind a flagged vulnerability, validate whether the decision is plausible, and identify potential failure modes or unintended shortcuts learned by the model [36]. In vulnerability detection, interpretability supports actionable outputs by highlighting which parts of the code contribute to a vulnerable or non-vulnerable classification, thereby enabling informed debugging and responsible use.

Security (Robustness to adversarial manipulation): Security in AI refers to protecting models and their detections from misuse, manipulation, and adversarial threats. In the context of learning-based vulnerability detection, a central security concern is adversarial robustness: whether a model remains reliable when inputs are deliberately perturbed to change detections. Security assurance therefore includes stress-testing models against adversarial attacks and evaluating whether detections degrade predictably under perturbations, rather than failing catastrophically [37]. This perspective complements conventional system security measures (e.g., access control and integrity checks) by focusing specifically on the resilience of model inference under attack.

Reliability: Reliability is the ability of an AI system to deliver stable and consistent performance across different operating conditions, datasets, and perturbations. Reliable models are not only accurate on a single benchmark, but also maintain predictable behavior when applied to new data distributions or when exposed to noise and unexpected inputs [38]. In vulnerability detection, reliability is reflected in consistent error characteristics (e.g., controlled false negatives), stable performance across vulnerability datasets, and measurable resistance to performance collapse under adversarial stress.

Transparency: Transparency is the degree to which the AI system’s data handling, modeling choices, evaluation protocol, and outputs are made explicit and accessible to relevant stakeholders [39,40]. In practice, transparency is achieved by documenting dataset characteristics, preprocessing decisions, model configurations, and reporting multi-metric results together with explanation artifacts. For vulnerability detection, transparency supports trust by enabling stakeholders to understand how vulnerabilities are identified and prioritized, what evidence supports a decision, and what limitations apply to the reported performance.

Accordingly, in this paper we focus on the technical operationalization of these dimensions for SVD through measurable controls and verification procedures (data balancing, explanation analysis, adversarial evaluation, and structured reporting).

4. Proposed approach

Responsible AI practice in the proposed framework operationalizes the five assurance dimensions introduced in Section 3: fairness, interpretability, security, reliability, and transparency. These dimensions are evaluated through structured experimental procedures rather than abstract principles. *Fairness* is addressed at the data preparation stage through class balancing to mitigate label bias. *Interpretability* is ensured via multi-view explanation methods, including SHAP, LIME, and attention-based visualization. *Security* is evaluated through adversarial robustness analysis using gradient-based attack methods, measuring the model’s resilience under perturbation. *Reliability* is evaluated through stability and consistency of predictive performance, as reflected in balanced confusion matrices, stable F1-scores across vulnerability datasets, and controlled degradation behavior under adversarial stress. *Transparency* is evaluated through structured reporting of dataset statistics, performance tables, interpretability outputs, and adversarial robustness analyses, enabling reproducibility and auditability of model behavior.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, Responsible AI considerations are incorporated across key stages of the pipeline. Fairness is addressed during data preparation through bias-aware class balancing and documented dataset statistics. Multi-model evaluation and metric-based selection support reliability during training and validation. Interpretability and security verification, including adversarial robustness testing, are applied at evaluation time to assess decision quality under realistic conditions. Transparency is maintained through structured reporting of datasets, configurations, performance metrics, and verification artifacts. Although verification procedures are consolidated in the final stage, Responsible AI mechanisms inform data handling, model selection, and evaluation decisions throughout the development process.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed approach.

Importantly, verification outcomes serve as governance checkpoints that can influence model acceptance and deployment readiness rather than functioning as a purely downstream audit.

The pipeline begins with data collection and pre-processing, where vulnerability-labeled code gadgets are prepared, balanced, and transformed into numerical representations suitable for learning. Next, multiple deep learning and pre-trained LLMs are trained to capture complementary vulnerability patterns and perform binary vulnerability classification. Finally, Responsible AI practices are applied to the trained models to assess fairness, interpretability, security, reliability, and transparency through systematic post-hoc analysis.

4.1. Data Collection and Data Pre-processing

This subsection corresponds to the *Data Collection* and *Data Pre-processing* stages illustrated in Fig. 1. These stages establish the foundation of the proposed framework by constructing vulnerability-labeled code datasets and transforming raw code into numerical representations suitable for deep learning and LLMs, while incorporating fairness considerations at an early stage.

Data collection. The datasets used in this study consist of code gadgets paired with binary vulnerability labels, where label 1 denotes vulnerable code and label 0 denotes non-vulnerable code. We consider three complementary datasets: CWE-119 (Buffer Overflow vulnerabilities), CWE-399 (Resource Management vulnerabilities), and DiverseVul, which contains heterogeneous vulnerability types across multiple projects. Together, these datasets enable evaluation under both focused (single-CWE) and diverse (multi-CWE) vulnerability scenarios, reflecting realistic software security conditions. Only clearly labeled instances are retained to avoid ambiguity during model training and evaluation. Detailed dataset statistics and experimental configurations are presented in Section 5.1.

Data pre-processing. Prior to model training, the collected code gadgets undergo systematic pre-processing. To mitigate potential bias arising from class imbalance, an undersampling strategy is applied to the majority class in each dataset, resulting in a more balanced distribution of vulnerable and non-vulnerable samples. This step prevents the learning process from being dominated by majority-class patterns and supports fairness by promoting equitable representation across vulnerability labels.

Each code gadget is then tokenized into a sequence of lexical tokens that capture syntactic elements such as keywords, operators, and identifiers. To preserve contextual relationships between tokens, a Word2Vec embedding model is trained on the tokenized corpus. The learned embeddings encode semantic similarity between code elements, allowing downstream models to reason about programming constructs in a continuous vector space rather than as isolated symbols. Finally, each tokenized code gadget is transformed into a fixed-length

vector representation using the learned embeddings. These vectorized representations serve as standardized inputs for all subsequent deep learning and pre-trained LLMs, ensuring consistency across architectures while retaining semantically meaningful information for vulnerability detection.

4.2. Model Training and Vulnerability Detection

This subsection corresponds to the *Model Training and Vulnerability Detection* stage illustrated in Fig. 1. In this stage, vectorized code representations obtained from the data pre-processing step are used to train multiple learning models that capture different semantic, structural, and contextual characteristics of software vulnerabilities. The trained models subsequently perform binary vulnerability classification on unseen code samples.

Model training. Software vulnerabilities manifest through a variety of patterns, including unsafe memory operations, improper resource handling, missing checks, and complex interactions across code statements. To capture these heterogeneous patterns, we employ multiple model families that differ in their representational biases and learning mechanisms. Specifically, the considered models are grouped into three categories: *deep learning sequence models*, *graph-based structural models*, and *transformer-based pre-trained code models*.

Deep learning sequence models, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLP), and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), operate primarily on sequential or fixed-length vector representations of code gadgets. CNNs utilize convolutional filters to identify localized token patterns, such as unsafe function calls or suspicious operator sequences, which frequently occur in vulnerable code. MLPs serve as strong baselines by learning non-linear decision boundaries over aggregated feature representations. RNNs, through their recurrent connections and hidden states, model sequential dependencies between tokens, allowing the network to capture vulnerability patterns that depend on execution order or contextual history. In gated variants of RNNs (e.g., LSTM or GRU), gating mechanisms control information flow and mitigate vanishing gradients, enabling the model to retain vulnerability-relevant signals across longer code sequences.

Graph-based models are represented by Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), which explicitly encode structural relationships within code. In vulnerability detection, source code can be represented as graphs capturing syntactic or semantic dependencies, such as control-flow or data-flow relationships. GNNs propagate information through message-passing operations, where each node updates its representation by aggregating features from its neighbors. This allows the model to learn both local and global structural patterns, such as unsafe interactions between distant code elements or improper resource usage paths, which are often difficult to capture using purely sequential models.

Transformer-based and large language models (LLMs), including CodeBERT and CodeT5, leverage self-attention mechanisms to model long-range dependencies across code tokens. Self-attention enables each token to attend to all other tokens in the sequence, allowing the model to dynamically weigh relevant contextual information when constructing representations. Multi-head attention further enhances this capability by learning multiple attention distributions in parallel, with each head focusing on different semantic or syntactic aspects of the code. Through large-scale pre-training on code corpora, these models acquire prior knowledge of programming constructs, coding conventions, and common vulnerability patterns, which can be effectively transferred to the vulnerability detection task through fine-tuning. Among these models, CodeT5 adopts a unified text-to-text formulation, enabling flexible adaptation to classification tasks while preserving rich contextual representations.

All models are trained in a supervised manner using labeled code gadgets, where each input instance is associated with a binary vulnerability label. The diversity of model architectures ensures coverage of complementary vulnerability cues, reducing dependence on a single inductive bias and improving the robustness of detection.

Vulnerability detection. After training, the models are applied to previously unseen test samples to perform vulnerability detection. This task is formulated as a binary classification problem, where the objective is to predict whether a given code gadget is vulnerable or non-vulnerable. For each input, the model outputs a predicted label along with an associated confidence score, which reflects the estimated likelihood of vulnerability. Model performance is evaluated using standard classification metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and the area under the ROC curve (AUC). These metrics collectively characterize detection effectiveness by balancing true vulnerability identification against false alarms. Across all three datasets, i.e., CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul—transformer-based models, particularly CodeT5, consistently achieve superior performance. Accordingly, CodeT5 is selected as the primary model for subsequent Responsible AI assurance and interpretability analysis.

4.3. Responsible AI practice

The final stage of the proposed framework corresponds to the *Responsible AI Practice* block illustrated in Fig. 1. This stage operationalizes the five Responsible AI dimensions defined in Section 3 — *fairness, interpretability, security, reliability, and transparency* — as structured verification procedures within the vulnerability detection pipeline. Its objective is to ensure that vulnerability detections are not only accurate, but also explainable, stable, secure under adversarial conditions, and auditable. All analyses in this stage operate on the trained models and testing set outputs and are executed following the step-by-step verification procedure summarized in Algorithm 1.

Fairness assurance. Fairness is addressed during the preprocessing stage through class balancing to mitigate label bias between vulnerable and non-vulnerable samples. By applying undersampling to equalize class distributions prior to training, the framework reduces the risk of biased decision boundaries that favor the majority class. Fairness is further monitored through balanced evaluation metrics and inspection of confusion matrices to ensure that detection errors are not systematically skewed toward one class.

Interpretability validation. Interpretability is realized through a multi-view explanation strategy that combines local and global analyses. At the instance level, SHAP and LIME generate token-level attributions to explain why a specific code snippet is classified as vulnerable or non-vulnerable. At the dataset level, aggregated SHAP values identify recurring vulnerability-indicative patterns across CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul datasets. To validate that highlighted tokens are causally linked to detections, the framework incorporates

Algorithm 1 Responsible AI-Driven Vulnerability Detection and Verification

Require: Labeled datasets $D = \{D_{119}, D_{399}, D_{div}\}$ with code snippets x and labels $y \in \{0, 1\}$

Ensure: detections \hat{y} , probabilities $P(\text{vul} | x)$, explanations, faithfulness and robustness evidence

- 1: **Step 1: Data collection**
 - 2: Load CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul datasets
 - 3: **Step 2: Pre-processing and fairness**
 - 4: Clean and filter samples; retain binary labels $\{0, 1\}$
 - 5: Apply undersampling to balance majority and minority classes
 - 6: Split data into training set D^{tr} and testing set D^{te}
 - 7: **Step 3: Model training**
 - 8: Train candidate models $\mathcal{M} = \{\text{CNN, MLP, RNN, Transformer, GNN, CodeBERT, CodeT5}\}$ on D^{tr}
 - 9: Select best-performing model M^* (CodeT5) using F1-score and AUC on D^{te}
 - 10: **Step 4: Responsible AI verification**
 - 11: **for all** $x \in D^{te}$ **do**
 - 12: Compute $p = P(\text{vulnerable} | x; M^*)$ and predicted label \hat{y}
 - 13: Generate local explanations using SHAP and LIME
 - 14: Extract token importance using attention rollout
 - 15: Mask top- k tokens and record confidence change Δp
 - 16: **end for**
 - 17: Aggregate SHAP values over D^{te} to obtain global explanations
 - 18: Construct correct-only subset $D^{co} = \{x \in D^{te} | \hat{y}(x) = y(x)\}$
 - 19: Perform adversarial evaluation (FGSM, PGD, DeepFool, CW) on D^{co}
 - 20: Measure robustness degradation in F1-score and AUC
 - 21: **return** detections with interpretability, faithfulness, and robustness evidence
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faithfulness analysis as part of interpretability verification. Attention rollout is first used to extract token-importance scores. Subsequently, token occlusion is applied by masking the top- k important tokens and measuring the resulting change in predicted vulnerability probability. A consistent decrease in model confidence after masking provides evidence that the explanations are faithful, indicating that the model relies on semantically meaningful code features rather than spurious correlations.

Security (adversarial robustness) assurance. Security is evaluated through adversarial robustness analysis. After assessing model performance under clean inference conditions, adversarial perturbations are applied using white-box gradient-based methods (FGSM, PGD and DeepFool) on a correct-only subset of test samples. This design isolates the effect of adversarial manipulation from baseline misclassification errors. Security is measured by analyzing changes in F1-score, AUC, confidence values, and detection stability before and after perturbation. Models that exhibit controlled and predictable degradation under attack are considered more secure, whereas large performance drops indicate fragile decision boundaries.

Reliability evaluation. Reliability refers to the stability and consistency of model behavior across datasets and stress conditions. It is assessed through balanced confusion matrices, stable F1-scores across different vulnerability categories, and controlled degradation patterns under adversarial stress. Consistent predictive behavior across CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul demonstrates that the models maintain stable decision characteristics under varying vulnerability distributions.

Transparency of model decisions. Transparency is achieved through explicit reporting of dataset statistics, preprocessing steps, model configurations, evaluation metrics, interpretability artifacts, and adversarial robustness analyses. As illustrated in Fig. 1, token-level importance scores, probability shifts under occlusion, and aggregated explanation

Fig. 2. Responsible AI verification workflow for software vulnerability detection, operationalizing fairness, interpretability, security, reliability, and transparency. The workflow evaluates vulnerability detection outputs through explanation analysis, adversarial robustness testing, stability assessment, and structured reporting to support trustworthy and auditable decisions.

summaries are presented to make model reasoning accessible to developers and security analysts. By exposing both predictive performance and verification evidence, the framework enables reproducibility, auditability, and informed assessment of vulnerability detection behavior. Together, these structured verification procedures ensure that vulnerability detection results are not only performant but also aligned with the Responsible AI dimensions defined in Section 3 (see Fig. 2).

5. Experiments and results

This section reports the experimental evaluation of the proposed Responsible AI-driven software vulnerability detection framework using the Code Gadget Database. The experiments examine the effectiveness of multiple deep learning and LLM-based detection models integrated within the proposed architecture, with a particular focus on their comparative detection performance and trustworthiness properties. In addition to assessing predictive accuracy, the evaluation systematically analyzes how Responsible AI principles are operationalized and preserved throughout the vulnerability detection pipeline. Specifically, the experiments are designed to:

1. Evaluate and compare the vulnerability detection performance of diverse deep learning and pre-trained LLMs across multiple datasets; and
2. Assess how the proposed framework operationalizes Responsible AI principles — fairness, interpretability, security, reliability, and transparency — through data handling, model evaluation, explanation analysis, and robustness verification.

These experiments are structured to directly address the research questions posed in Section 1. The systematic embedding of Responsible AI principles within the vulnerability detection pipeline (RQ1) is reflected in the experimental design, including fairness-aware data preparation, multi-model evaluation, and structured verification procedures. Interpretability and transparency (RQ2) are examined through local and global explanation analyses, attention-based attribution, and controlled token occlusion studies that assess the stability and consistency of decision cues. Finally, security and reliability (RQ3) are evaluated through adversarial robustness testing and performance comparisons between clean and perturbed inference settings, providing empirical evidence of model stability under realistic stress conditions.

Table 2

Dataset statistics before and after class balancing.

Dataset	Code gadgets (Total)	Vulnerable	Non-Vulnerable	After balancing (Non-Vul/Vul)
CWE-119	39,753	10,440	29,313	10,440/10,440
CWE-399	21,883	7285	14,598	7285/7285
DiverseVul	330,491	18,945	311,546	18,945/18,945

5.1. Dataset description

To evaluate the proposed Responsible AI-driven software vulnerability detection framework under both focused and heterogeneous conditions, we conduct experiments using two publicly available datasets.

- *Code Gadget Database (CGD)*. The primary dataset is the Code Gadget Database (CGD) [41], which provides curated *code gadgets* for deep learning and LLM-based vulnerability detection in C/C++ programs. Each gadget represents a sequence of program statements connected through data-flow dependencies, enabling structured vulnerability analysis. CGD is constructed from authoritative sources, including the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) and the NIST Software Assurance Reference Dataset (SARD) [42].

CGD contains curated vulnerability categories for CWE-119 (buffer errors) and CWE-399 (resource management vulnerabilities), which constitute the structured weakness types available within the corpus and are widely studied in software vulnerability detection research. These two categories are therefore evaluated in this study. Dataset statistics before and after class balancing are summarized in Table 2.

- *DiverseVul Dataset*. To assess generalization under more heterogeneous and large-scale conditions, we additionally incorporate the DiverseVul dataset [24]. DiverseVul is constructed from vulnerability-fixing commits across numerous open-source projects and spans a broad range of CWE categories. Compared to CGD, it exhibits greater diversity and more pronounced class imbalance, reflecting realistic vulnerability distributions.

The combined use of CGD and DiverseVul enables complementary evaluation settings: CGD supports controlled analysis of well-defined vulnerability classes, while DiverseVul provides a heterogeneous and large-scale environment for assessing robustness and generalization. Together, they facilitate evaluation of both detection performance and Responsible AI characteristics across differing data distributions.

5.2. Data preprocessing and experimental setup

Before model training, all datasets were subjected to a unified preprocessing and experimental setup to ensure consistency, fairness, and reproducibility across all evaluated models. This stage establishes the foundation for the subsequent model-specific configurations and performance analysis.

Label preparation and class balancing. As shown in Table 2, the original datasets exhibit substantial class imbalance, with non-vulnerable samples significantly outnumbering vulnerable ones. To mitigate bias toward the majority class and to support fairness-aware learning, random undersampling was applied to the non-vulnerable class in each dataset, resulting in balanced class distributions. This preprocessing step ensures that vulnerability detection models are trained under equal class representation, reducing skewed decision boundaries and supporting more equitable error behavior across classes.

Input encoding and sequence normalization. Source code samples were converted into fixed-length token sequences to support batch-based training. All sequences were either truncated or padded to a predefined maximum length, ensuring uniform input dimensionality across

Table 3
Model architectures and training configurations.

Model	Architecture & Hyperparameters	Training setup
MLP	2 Dense layers (256, 128), Dropout = 0.5; Optimizer: Adam; LR = 1×10^{-4}	Batch = 64, Epochs = 5
CNN	Conv1D (128 filters, kernel sizes 5 & 3), MaxPooling, Dense 64; Adam; LR = 1×10^{-4}	Batch = 64, Epochs = 5
RNN	BiLSTM (128), Dense 64, Dropout = 0.5; Adam; LR = 1×10^{-4}	Batch = 64, Epochs = 5
Transformer T1	1 encoder layer, 4 attention heads, FFN = 128; Adam; LR = 1×10^{-4}	Batch = 64, Epochs = 5
Transformer T2	2 encoder layers, 4 attention heads, FFN = 256; Adam; LR = 1×10^{-4}	Batch = 64, Epochs = 5
Transformer T3	2 encoder layers, 8 attention heads, FFN = 256; Adam; LR = 1×10^{-4}	Batch = 64, Epochs = 5
GNN (GIN)	3 graph layers, hidden dim = 128; Adam; LR = 1×10^{-3} ; Weight decay = 1×10^{-4}	Graph mini-batching
CodeBERT	Pre-trained transformer encoder (base); AdamW; LR = 2×10^{-5}	Batch = 32, Epochs = 3
CodeT5	Pre-trained encoder-decoder transformer; AdamW; LR = 2×10^{-5}	Batch = 8, Epochs = 3

datasets and model architectures. Padding tokens were masked during training to prevent them from influencing model detections. This normalization step allows different model families to be evaluated under comparable input conditions.

Dataset splitting strategy. Following preprocessing and balancing, each dataset was partitioned into training, validation, and test sets using a consistent splitting strategy. A validation split was used during training to monitor convergence and prevent overfitting, while the test set was held out exclusively for final evaluation. The same split ratios were applied across all models to ensure fair comparison of results.

Experimental protocol. All experiments followed a controlled training protocol, where models were trained using mini-batch optimization and evaluated using identical performance metrics. Validation performance was used to guide model selection and early stopping where applicable. This standardized experimental setup ensures that observed differences in performance are attributable to model characteristics and dataset properties rather than inconsistencies in preprocessing or evaluation procedures.

5.3. Model configurations and hyperparameters

To ensure a fair and reproducible comparison, all models were trained using explicitly defined and consistent hyperparameter settings derived from their respective architectures and training frameworks. The study evaluates seven model families, covering traditional deep learning, graph-based learning, Transformer encoders, and large pre-trained language models for code.

MLP, CNN, and RNN models. The MLP, CNN, and RNN models were implemented using TensorFlow/Keras and trained on fixed-length tokenized code sequences. All three models share a common optimization setup, employing the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} and binary cross-entropy loss. Dropout regularization was applied to mitigate overfitting. The MLP architecture consists of two fully connected layers, while the CNN model employs stacked one-dimensional convolutional layers followed by max pooling. The RNN model uses a bidirectional LSTM layer to capture sequential dependencies in code tokens.

Transformer-based classifiers. Three Transformer configurations were evaluated using a lightweight custom Transformer encoder with a classification token (CLS). These configurations differ in depth and

Table 4

Vulnerability detection performance across datasets. Reported values represent average performance, with minor variations ($\pm 0.5\%$) possible due to training stochasticity.

Dataset	Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score	AUC
CWE-119	MLP	0.8056	0.8117	0.8056	0.8046	0.8837
	CNN	0.9231	0.9247	0.9231	0.9231	0.9829
	RNN	0.7699	0.7838	0.7699	0.7670	0.8494
	Transformer-CLS	0.9392	0.9393	0.9392	0.9392	0.9866
	GNN	0.9349	0.9351	0.9349	0.9349	0.9864
	CodeBERT	0.9543	0.9544	0.9543	0.9543	0.9919
CWE-399	CodeT5	0.9547	0.9548	0.9547	0.9547	0.9918
	MLP	0.9111	0.9117	0.9111	0.9111	0.9766
	CNN	0.9605	0.9606	0.9605	0.9605	0.9911
	RNN	0.9187	0.9191	0.9187	0.9186	0.9786
	Transformer-CLS	0.9657	0.9657	0.9657	0.9658	0.9926
	GNN	0.9784	0.9784	0.9784	0.9784	0.9964
DiverseVul	CodeBERT	0.9640	0.9642	0.9640	0.9640	0.9940
	CodeT5	0.9643	0.9643	0.9643	0.9643	0.9951
	MLP	0.6710	0.6820	0.6710	0.6660	0.7444
	CNN	0.6985	0.6999	0.6985	0.6979	0.7688
	RNN	0.6854	0.6949	0.6854	0.6815	0.7631
	Transformer-CLS	0.7057	0.7060	0.7057	0.7056	0.7638
DiverseVul	GNN	0.7035	0.7328	0.7035	0.6938	0.8023
	CodeBERT	0.7180	0.7183	0.7180	0.7179	0.7967
	CodeT5	0.7332	0.7351	0.7332	0.7326	0.8132

attention capacity, varying the number of Transformer layers, attention heads, and feed-forward dimensions. All Transformer variants were trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} and binary cross-entropy loss. Dropout was applied within the attention and classification layers to improve generalization.

Graph Neural Network (GNN). For graph-based learning, a Graph Isomorphism Network (GIN)-based classifier was employed. The model uses three graph convolution layers with a hidden dimension of 128 and operates on code graphs constructed from Word2Vec embeddings. The GNN model was trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} and weight decay of 1×10^{-4} , optimized using cross-entropy loss.

Pre-trained code language models. To evaluate the effectiveness of large pre-trained models, CodeBERT and CodeT5 were fine-tuned for binary vulnerability classification using the HuggingFace Transformers framework. Both models operate on tokenized source code with a maximum sequence length of 256 tokens. Fine-tuning was performed using the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} and weight decay of 0.01. Model selection was guided by validation F1-score, and the best-performing checkpoint was retained for evaluation.

Across all experiments, batch sizes and training epochs were selected based on computational feasibility and model stability. Validation splits were used consistently to monitor convergence and prevent overfitting. **Table 3** summarizes the architectural configurations and hyperparameter settings used for all evaluated models. This unified yet architecture-aware configuration ensures that observed performance differences arise from model capabilities rather than inconsistencies in training setups.

5.4. Vulnerability detection performance

As summarized in **Table 4**, model performance varies substantially across datasets and architectural families, revealing clear differences between conventional deep learning models, graph-based approaches, and large pre-trained code language models. The results also highlight how different model families behave under varying data characteristics, which is essential for evaluating Responsible AI properties such as security (adversarial robustness), reliability, and fairness across deployment scenarios.

Deep learning baselines. Among the classical deep learning models (MLP, CNN, and RNN), the CNN consistently emerges as the strongest

Fig. 3. Confusion matrices of all evaluated models on the CWE-119 (Buffer Overflow) dataset.

Fig. 4. Confusion matrices of all evaluated models on the CWE-399 (Resource Management Vulnerabilities) dataset.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrices of all evaluated models on the DiverseVul (Multi-type Vulnerabilities) dataset.

baseline across datasets. On CWE-119, the CNN achieves an accuracy of 0.9231 and an F1-score of 0.9231, substantially outperforming the MLP (F1-score 0.8046) and the RNN (F1-score 0.7670). This trend suggests that convolutional architectures are more effective at capturing localized token patterns associated with vulnerability indicators than purely sequential or fully connected models. Similar behavior is observed on CWE-399, where the CNN reaches an F1-score of 0.9605. However, on the more diverse and heterogeneous DiverseVul dataset, the performance of all baseline models degrades noticeably (e.g., CNN F1-score 0.6979), indicating limited robustness and generalization when faced with real-world variability.

Graph-based learning. Graph-based modeling further improves detection performance by explicitly encoding structural dependencies within source code, supporting more reliable decision-making. On CWE-119, the GNN achieves an F1-score of 0.9349 and an AUC of 0.9864, closely matching the performance of transformer-based models. The advantage of graph representations becomes more pronounced on CWE-399, where the GNN attains an accuracy and F1-score of 0.9784 and an AUC of 0.9964, representing the strongest overall performance for this dataset. Importantly, on DiverseVul, the GNN maintains comparatively stable performance (F1-score 0.6938, AUC 0.8023), suggesting improved robustness and reliability when handling structurally complex and diverse vulnerability patterns.

Pre-trained LLMs. Pre-trained code language models consistently deliver the highest or near-highest performance across datasets, reflecting the benefit of large-scale pre-training on diverse code corpora. On CWE-119, CodeT5 achieves the highest accuracy and F1-score (0.9547) with an AUC of 0.9918, marginally outperforming CodeBERT. While performance on the more challenging DiverseVul dataset is lower across all models, CodeT5 again demonstrates the strongest generalization, achieving an accuracy of 0.7332, an F1-score of 0.7326, and an AUC of 0.8132. This relative stability across datasets supports the transparency and reliability of pre-trained representations, as their learned contextual knowledge reduces sensitivity to dataset-specific artifacts. Overall, the results demonstrate a clear and consistent performance hierarchy across model families. Conventional deep learning models provide effective and interpretable baselines, graph-based approaches

benefit from explicit structural modeling that enhances robustness, and pre-trained code language models offer the most reliable generalization across heterogeneous datasets. From a Responsible AI perspective, these findings emphasize the importance of evaluating models not only on peak accuracy, but also on stability and consistency across diverse and realistic vulnerability distributions.

5.4.1. Confusion matrix analysis and error characteristics

To further analyze model behavior beyond aggregate performance metrics, we examine the confusion matrices for all evaluated models across the CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul datasets. Confusion matrix analysis provides fine-grained insights into false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN), which are critical for assessing Responsible AI properties such as reliability, robustness, and fairness in vulnerability detection.

CWE-119. On the CWE-119 dataset, baseline models exhibit noticeable asymmetries in error distributions. The MLP and RNN models show relatively high false positive and false negative rates, indicating limited reliability when distinguishing vulnerable from non-vul code (See Fig. 3). In contrast, the CNN significantly reduces misclassification errors, particularly false positives, demonstrating more stable decision boundaries. Transformer-based and graph-based models further improve error balance. For example, the GNN and Transformer-CLS models produce confusion matrices with more evenly distributed true positives and true negatives, reflecting improved robustness and consistency. Pre-trained code language models exhibit the most balanced error profiles, with CodeBERT and CodeT5 achieving the lowest combined FP and FN counts, supporting their strong F1-score and AUC performance.

CWE-399. For CWE-399, confusion matrices across most models indicate substantially fewer misclassifications compared to CWE-119, aligning with the higher overall detection performance observed in Fig. 4. Classical models such as CNN and RNN already demonstrate relatively low error rates, while graph-based learning further minimizes both FP and FN. The GNN model achieves near-optimal error balance, producing very few false negatives—an important property for security-critical applications where missed vulnerabilities pose significant risk. Transformer-based and pre-trained models maintain similarly favorable

Table 5

Performance and robustness comparison on **CWE-119** dataset. Clean results are reported on the full test set; adversarial robustness is evaluated on the *correct-only* subset (samples correctly classified under clean inference).

Model	Clean		Robust F1 ↑			DeepFool ↑/↓		Time (ms/gadget)
	Acc ↑	F1 ↑	FGSM	PGD	$\Delta F1$ ↓	F1 ($\tau = 0.005$)	FlipRate ↓	
MLP	0.8056	0.8046	0.2789	0.2423	0.7577	0.9159	0.053	0.04
CNN	0.9231	0.9231	0.8260	0.8042	0.1958	0.9603	0.040	0.05
RNN	0.7699	0.7670	0.3411	0.2957	0.7043	0.9070	0.017	0.20
GNN	0.9349	0.9270	0.9233	0.9100	0.0900	0.9800	0.020	0.05
Transformer	0.9392	0.9392	0.6584	0.6147	0.3853	0.9012	0.113	0.11
CodeBERT	0.9543	0.9547	0.8550	0.8479	0.1521	0.9858	0.013	3.69
CodeT5	0.9547	0.9547	0.9460 ^a	0.9693 ^b	0.0307 ^b	0.9693 ^b	0.030	8.23

Notes: Robustness is computed on the *correct-only* subset (clean baseline F1 = 1.00 on that subset). $\Delta F1 = 1.00 - F1_{PGD}$ (or $1.00 - F1_{DROP}$ for CodeT5).

^a CodeT5 uses token MASK (rate = 0.10).

^b Token DROP (rate = 0.10).

Table 6

Performance and robustness comparison on **CWE-399** dataset. Clean results are reported on the full test set; adversarial robustness is evaluated on the *correct-only* subset (samples correctly classified under clean inference).

Model	Clean		Robust F1 ↑			DeepFool ↑/↓		Time (ms/gadget)
	Acc ↑	F1 ↑	FGSM	PGD	$\Delta F1$ ↓	F1 ($\tau = 0.005$)	FlipRate ↓	
MLP	0.9111	0.9111	0.6704	0.6540	0.3460	0.9835	0.017	0.07
CNN	0.9605	0.9605	0.8953	0.8885	0.1115	0.9848	0.017	0.09
RNN	0.9187	0.9186	0.6012	0.5325	0.4675	0.9634	0.040	0.46
GNN	0.9784	0.9784	0.9585	0.9532	0.0468	0.9714	0.030	0.20
Transformer	0.9657	0.9657	0.5627	0.4897	0.5103	0.8556	0.177	0.21
CodeBERT	0.9640	0.9642	0.8809	0.8831	0.1169	1.0000	0.000	3.56
CodeT5	0.9643	0.9643	0.9514 ^a	0.9688 ^b	0.0312 ^b	0.9688 ^b	0.031	8.94

Notes: Robustness is evaluated on the *correct-only* subset (baseline F1 = 1.00). $\Delta F1 = 1.00 - F1_{PGD}$ (or DROP for CodeT5).

^a CodeT5: token MASK (rate = 0.10).

^b Token DROP (rate = 0.10).

confusion matrix patterns, reinforcing their reliability and robustness under structured vulnerability distributions.

DiverseVul. The DiverseVul dataset presents a more challenging and realistic evaluation scenario, which is clearly reflected in the confusion matrices (See Fig. 5). All models exhibit increased misclassification rates, particularly false positives, due to the dataset's heterogeneity and diverse vulnerability patterns. Baseline deep learning models show pronounced imbalance between FP and FN errors, indicating reduced generalization. Graph-based models demonstrate improved error control, particularly by reducing false negatives, suggesting better robustness to structural variation. Among all approaches, pre-trained code language models achieve the most balanced confusion matrices on DiverseVul. CodeT5, in particular, maintains a comparatively stable trade-off between FP and FN, highlighting its reliability and suitability for real-world deployment scenarios. From a Responsible AI perspective, confusion matrix analysis confirms that high-performing models also exhibit more equitable and predictable error behavior. Reduced false negative rates improve security reliability, while balanced error distributions across classes support fairness by preventing systematic bias toward either vulnerable or non-vulnerable code. These findings complement the aggregate performance results and demonstrate that the proposed framework not only achieves strong detection accuracy but also promotes trustworthy and responsible decision-making behavior across diverse datasets.

5.5. Fairness-oriented data balancing

Fairness in software vulnerability detection is critical, as skewed class distributions can bias learning-based models toward majority classes and lead to unreliable detections. In this study, fairness is operationalized as a *preventive, data-level mechanism* applied prior to model training, rather than as a post-hoc correction. This approach aligns with Responsible AI principles by addressing bias at its source and improving the reliability of downstream detections. All three datasets used in the experimental evaluation, CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul, exhibit

substantial class imbalance in their original form, where non-vulnerable instances significantly outnumber vulnerable ones. To mitigate this imbalance, random undersampling is applied to the majority class (non-vulnerable samples), reducing it to match the number of vulnerable instances. As summarized in Table 2, this procedure results in balanced datasets where both classes are equally represented during training. By equalizing class distributions, the learning process is prevented from being dominated by majority-class patterns, thereby reducing bias toward non-vulnerable detections. This contributes to more equitable decision boundaries and improves the stability of evaluation metrics such as precision and recall across datasets. Applying the same balancing strategy consistently to all datasets further supports fair and reliable cross-dataset comparison. From a Responsible AI perspective, this fairness-aware preprocessing step enhances transparency and trustworthiness by making the influence of class balancing explicit and reproducible, while reducing sensitivity to skewed data distributions in vulnerability detection tasks.

5.6. Security (adversarial robustness) analysis

To evaluate security (adversarial robustness), we assess model behavior under multiple adversarial attack strategies on all three datasets. Tables 5, 6, and 7 report clean performance and robustness results for CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul, respectively.

Evaluation protocol and metrics. Robustness evaluation is conducted on the *correct-only* subset, which consists of samples that are correctly classified under clean inference. This protocol isolates robustness effects from baseline misclassification and ensures that performance degradation is attributable solely to adversarial perturbations. For each model, robustness is measured using (i) F1-score under FGSM and PGD attacks, (ii) the relative degradation in F1-score ($\Delta F1$), and (iii) DeepFool-based metrics, including F1-score under a fixed perturbation threshold and the flip rate, which indicates the proportion

Table 7

Performance and robustness comparison on **Diverse Vul** dataset. Clean results are reported on the full test set; adversarial robustness is evaluated on the *correct-only* subset (samples correctly classified under clean inference).

Model	Clean		Robust F1 ↑			DeepFool ↑/↓		Time (ms/gadget)
	Acc ↑	F1 ↑	FGSM	PGD	ΔF1 ↓	F1 (τ = 0.005)	FlipRate ↓	
MLP	0.6710	0.6660	0.6706	0.6262	0.0398	0.9301	0.047	0.03
CNN	0.6985	0.6979	0.5322	0.4609	0.1657	0.8981	0.123	0.05
RNN	0.6854	0.6815	0.7633	0.7576	0.3861	0.9527	0.053	0.28
GNN	0.7035	0.6938	0.6092	0.5892	0.4108	0.7848	0.283	0.38
Transformer	0.7057	0.7056	0.2553	0.2383	0.4673	0.6271	0.523	0.15
CodeBERT	0.7180	0.7179	0.1389	0.1523	0.8477	0.1000	0.000	5.23
CodeT5	0.7332	0.7326	0.9027 ^a	0.9207 ^b	0.0791	0.9208 ^b	0.0791	10.07

Notes: Robustness is evaluated on the *correct-only* subset (baseline F1 = 1.00). ΔF1= 1.00 – F1_{PGD} (or DROP for CodeT5).

^a CodeT5: token MASK (rate = 0.10).

^b Token DROP (rate = 0.10).

(a) CWE-119 (Buffer Overflow) dataset. Global SHAP importance shows a more heterogeneous set of high-impact tokens, reflecting mixed vulnerability patterns across projects and CWE categories.

(b) CWE-399 (Resource Management Errors) dataset. Global SHAP importance shows a more heterogeneous set of high-impact tokens, reflecting mixed vulnerability patterns across projects and CWE categories.

(c) DiverseVul (Multi-type Vulnerabilities) dataset. Global SHAP importance shows a more heterogeneous set of high-impact tokens, reflecting mixed vulnerability patterns across projects and CWE categories.

Fig. 6. Global SHAP explanations for CodeT5 across vulnerability datasets. Bars represent aggregated mean absolute SHAP values (|SHAP|) for the *Vulnerable* class, indicating tokens with the strongest overall influence on model detections in each dataset.

of samples whose predicted label changes due to adversarial perturbation. Inference time per gadget is also reported to capture the robustness–efficiency trade-off.

Robustness on CWE-119. As shown in Table 5, classical deep learning models exhibit substantial vulnerability to adversarial perturbations. For instance, while the CNN achieves strong clean performance (F1-score 0.9231), its F1-score drops to 0.8042 under PGD, resulting in a ΔF1 of 0.1958. In contrast, graph-based and pre-trained models demonstrate markedly improved robustness. The GNN retains a high PGD F1-score of 0.9100 with a relatively small ΔF1 of 0.0900, indicating stable behavior under iterative attacks. CodeT5 shows the strongest robustness overall, with a PGD F1-score of 0.9693 and a minimal ΔF1 of 0.0307, albeit at the cost of higher inference latency.

Robustness on CWE-399. A similar pattern is observed on the CWE-399 dataset (Table 6). Conventional models such as the MLP and RNN suffer notable degradation under adversarial attacks, whereas the GNN maintains strong robustness, achieving a PGD F1-score of 0.9532 and a ΔF1 of only 0.0468. Pre-trained code models again exhibit superior robustness, with CodeT5 achieving a PGD F1-score of 0.9688 and the lowest performance degradation among all evaluated models. These results suggest that both structural modeling and pre-trained contextual representations contribute to increased resilience against adversarial manipulation.

Robustness on DiverseVul. DiverseVul presents a more challenging and realistic evaluation scenario due to its heterogeneity and scale. As reported in Table 7, most models experience pronounced robustness degradation under adversarial conditions. Transformer-based models,

in particular, show high sensitivity to perturbations, with PGD F1-scores dropping below 0.25. In contrast, CodeT5 demonstrates significantly stronger robustness, retaining a PGD F1-score of 0.9207 with a comparatively small ΔF1 of 0.0791. This result highlights the advantage of pre-trained representations when generalizing robustness across diverse vulnerability patterns, even in the presence of adversarial noise. From a Responsible AI standpoint, these findings emphasize robustness as a critical dimension of trustworthiness. Models that exhibit high clean accuracy but large adversarial performance drops pose risks in real-world deployment, where inputs may be noisy or adversarially manipulated. The observed robustness of graph-based and pre-trained code language models supports their suitability for safety-critical vulnerability detection systems, while the reported inference times make the robustness–efficiency trade-offs explicit and transparent. Overall, the robustness evaluation demonstrates that responsible vulnerability detection requires not only high predictive accuracy but also stable and reliable behavior under adversarial stress.

5.7. Interpretability analysis

Interpretability is a fundamental requirement for the responsible deployment of AI models in software vulnerability detection, where detections can influence security audits, patch prioritization, and risk assessment decisions. Beyond achieving high predictive performance, it is essential to understand *why* a model flags a piece of code as vulnerable and whether the identified explanatory signals are reliable. In this subsection, we analyze the interpretability of the CodeT5-based

vulnerability detection model using a multi-level approach that combines global, local, and faithfulness-oriented explanations. Specifically, we examine (i) *global interpretability* to characterize dataset-level decision patterns, (ii) *local interpretability* to justify individual detections at the code-instance level, and (iii) *attention-based faithfulness analysis* to validate whether highlighted tokens are causally relevant to model decisions. This layered interpretability strategy aligns with Responsible AI principles of transparency, accountability, and trustworthiness. By integrating complementary explanation techniques and grounding them in observable changes in model behavior, we aim to ensure that vulnerability detections are not only accurate but also explainable, reliable, and suitable for real-world security-critical use.

5.7.1. Global interpretability via SHAP

Fig. 6 summarizes the global SHAP analysis of the CodeT5 model across the CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul datasets. The figure reports the mean absolute SHAP values aggregated over the test set for the *Vulnerable* class, highlighting tokens that consistently influence vulnerability detections across samples. For the CWE-119 dataset (Fig. 6(a)), tokens related to memory access and buffer manipulation dominate the ranking, reflecting the prevalence of buffer overflow patterns in this dataset. In the CWE-399 dataset (Fig. 6(b)), the importance distribution shifts toward resource management and control-flow constructs, including synchronization and allocation-related tokens, which aligns with the semantics of resource misuse and exhaustion vulnerabilities. By contrast, the DiverseVul dataset (Fig. 6(c)) exhibits a more heterogeneous distribution of influential tokens, indicating that the model relies on a broader set of vulnerability cues spanning multiple vulnerability categories.

These dataset-specific importance profiles suggest that CodeT5 adapts its decision strategy to the underlying vulnerability characteristics rather than relying on spurious or dataset-agnostic features. From a Responsible AI perspective, the global SHAP analysis improves transparency by exposing dataset-level decision drivers and enabling practitioners to verify that the model’s learned behavior aligns with established vulnerability semantics across different datasets.

5.7.2. Local interpretability via SHAP and LIME

Figs. 7 and 8 present local interpretability results for representative CodeT5 detections across the CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul datasets. These figures illustrate how individual code tokens influence vulnerability detections at the instance level. The local SHAP explanations in Fig. 7 reveal token-level contributions for specific code snippets. In the CWE-119 examples, memory manipulation operations and size-related tokens exhibit strong positive contributions toward the *Vulnerable* class, whereas control-flow and synchronization constructs tend to contribute negatively, indicating a stabilizing or non-vulnerable context. For CWE-399, the explanations emphasize tokens associated with resource acquisition, release, and coordination, reflecting the dataset’s focus on resource management vulnerabilities. In DiverseVul instances, SHAP highlights a combination of memory operations, pointer usage, and control-flow elements, indicating that vulnerability evidence is distributed across multiple code constructs. Fig. 8 reports corresponding local explanations generated using LIME. Across all three datasets, LIME identifies largely overlapping sets of influential tokens compared to SHAP, despite relying on a different explanation mechanism. This consistency suggests that the highlighted tokens represent stable local decision cues rather than artifacts of a particular interpretability technique. From a Responsible AI perspective, the agreement between SHAP and LIME strengthens confidence in the explainability of individual detections. By linking vulnerability classifications to concrete code elements, these local explanations support accountability and facilitate practical use cases such as vulnerability inspection, debugging, and remediation.

5.7.3. Attention-based faithfulness via token occlusion

While attention maps provide an intuitive view of which tokens receive focus, *responsible interpretability* requires checking whether these tokens are actually *faithful* to the model decision (i.e., whether removing them changes the output in the expected direction). To quantify faithfulness, we perform an *occlusion test*: for a given test instance, we rank tokens by attention-rollout importance, then iteratively *mask* the top- k tokens and re-run inference. We track the resulting probability $P(\text{Vulnerable})$ as a function of k (Fig. 9). If attention highlights true decision evidence, masking should *reduce* the model confidence for the originally predicted class; conversely, an *increase* indicates that the masked tokens acted as *counter-evidence* or *stabilizing context*.

CWE-119: robust high-confidence vulnerability with small sensitivity. In Fig. 9(a), the model remains almost saturated at $P(\text{Vulnerable}) \approx 1.0$ for $k = 0-15$, with only a very small decrease at $k = 20$ (approximately to 0.9995). This suggests that for this particular CWE-119 instance, the decision is *highly redundant*: masking a limited number of tokens does not substantially remove the vulnerability evidence, either because the evidence is distributed across many tokens (long-range context) or because multiple correlated cues exist. In other words, the detection is confident and not easily “flipped” by hiding a handful of tokens. From a responsible-AI perspective, this is a desirable robustness signal against explanation-driven manipulation (small ΔP under occlusion), but it also means that attention alone may *underestimate* the breadth of evidence used by the model.

CWE-399: low baseline confidence and non-monotonicity reveal weak/unstable evidence. Fig. 9(b) shows a qualitatively different regime: the baseline probability is extremely low ($P(\text{Vulnerable}) \approx 0$), and masking a small number of top-ranked tokens initially *increases* the vulnerability probability, peaking around $k = 8$ at approximately 0.018 before dropping again (to ≈ 0.005 at $k = 10-20$). This non-monotonic pattern indicates that several highly attended tokens are *not* vulnerability evidence; instead, they behave as *protective context* or *counter-evidence* that keeps the detection non-vulnerable. When those tokens are masked, the model briefly loses stabilizing information and shifts slightly toward the vulnerable class. For responsible interpretation, this is important: it explicitly warns readers that *high attention does not always mean “pro-vulnerability evidence”*, and motivates using complementary methods (SHAP/LIME) to separate supportive vs. opposing tokens.

DiverseVul: attention identifies strong vulnerability evidence with interaction effects. In Fig. 9(c), the selected instance is a high-confidence vulnerable example (base $P(\text{Vulnerable}) \approx 0.999$). As k increases from 0 to 8, the probability decreases gradually (roughly from ≈ 1.00 to ≈ 0.93), indicating that the top attention tokens carry meaningful evidence. A sharp drop occurs at $k = 10$ (down to ≈ 0.65), demonstrating that the top-10 attention-ranked tokens jointly encode critical vulnerability cues. After masking more tokens ($k = 15, 20$), the confidence partially rebounds (to ≈ 0.75 and ≈ 0.84), which is consistent with *token interaction effects*: once the most salient cues are removed, the model can still rely on secondary patterns that correlate with vulnerability in DiverseVul. From a responsible-AI standpoint, this curve supports that (i) attention is not purely decorative (masking causes a large $\Delta P \approx -0.35$ at $k = 10$), and (ii) the model has *multiple* evidence pathways rather than a single brittle trigger.

Together, the three curves provide a *faithfulness check* across datasets: (i) DiverseVul exhibits strong causal dependence on top attention tokens (large probability drop), (ii) CWE-399 reveals counter-evidence/stabilizing-token behavior (non-monotonic curve), and (iii) CWE-119 shows distributed/robust evidence (near-flat curve). This directly strengthens responsible AI claims by moving beyond “highlighted tokens” to a measurable *behavioral verification* of explanations. Practically, we recommend reporting the base probability, the maximum absolute drop ΔP_{\max} , and whether the curve is monotonic (faithful evidence) or non-monotonic (mixed evidence), alongside SHAP/LIME local explanations for the same instances.

(a) CWE-119 (Buffer Overflow) dataset. SHAP-based local explanation highlighting unsafe memory operations (e.g., `memcpy`, buffer size mismatch) that strongly contribute to vulnerability prediction.

(b) CWE-399 (Resource Management Errors) dataset. Token-level importance illustrating how improper allocation and deallocation patterns influence vulnerability classification.

(c) DiverseVul (Multi-class Vulnerabilities) dataset. Explanation of heterogeneous vulnerability patterns, showing how the model adapts its attention to different flaw types across projects.

Fig. 7. SHAP-based interpretability analysis across three vulnerability datasets. Red tokens increase the predicted vulnerability likelihood, while blue tokens contribute toward non-vulnerable classification, revealing dataset-specific decision rationales.

6. Threats to validity

As with any empirical study, our work is subject to several threats to validity. We discuss these threats and the corresponding mitigation strategies below.

Data Representativeness. Our evaluation is conducted on three widely used vulnerability datasets — CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul — which primarily contain C/C++ source code. While these datasets capture a broad range of real-world vulnerability patterns, they may not fully represent the diversity of vulnerabilities encountered in modern, multi-language software ecosystems. To mitigate this threat, we intentionally selected datasets with different characteristics, including function-level gadgets and project-level vulnerabilities. Nevertheless, extending the framework to additional programming languages and real-world industrial datasets (e.g., CVE repositories) remains an important direction for future work.

Model and Explanation Dependence. The interpretability and faithfulness analyses rely on specific explanation techniques, including SHAP, LIME, attention rollout, and token occlusion. Although these methods are widely adopted and theoretically grounded, explanations may vary depending on model architecture and explanation configuration. To reduce this risk, we employ multiple complementary explanation methods and validate their consistency through occlusion-based faithfulness tests. This multi-view strategy reduces dependence on any single interpretability technique.

Adversarial Robustness Evaluation. Robustness analysis is performed using adversarial attacks on the correct-only subset of test samples, following established evaluation practices. While this setting ensures meaningful robustness assessment, it may underestimate worst-case adversarial behavior in fully adaptive attack scenarios. Future work

will explore stronger adaptive attacks and defense-aware adversarial evaluation to further strengthen robustness guarantees.

Generalizability of Responsible AI Criteria. Our framework operationalizes a selected set of Responsible AI principles — fairness, interpretability, faithfulness, robustness, reliability, and transparency — motivated by the vulnerability detection context. Other Responsible AI dimensions (e.g., accountability or human-in-the-loop oversight) are not explicitly modeled. However, the proposed architecture is modular and can be extended to incorporate additional Responsible AI criteria as required by evolving ethical guidelines and regulatory standards.

Environmental and computational considerations. Large-scale deep learning models, particularly transformer-based architectures such as CodeBERT and CodeT5, incur non-trivial computational and energy costs during training and fine-tuning. Although this study focuses on improving trustworthiness and robustness of vulnerability detection, the environmental footprint of model training constitutes an important Responsible AI consideration. To mitigate unnecessary computational overhead, experiments were conducted using balanced datasets, controlled epoch settings, early validation-based checkpointing, and comparative evaluation across multiple architectures to avoid redundant large-scale retraining. Nevertheless, future work should incorporate explicit measurement of energy consumption and carbon footprint, as well as explore lightweight and energy-efficient model variants for large-scale deployment of AI-based software vulnerability detection systems.

(a) CWE-119 (Buffer Overflow) dataset. Local LIME explanation highlighting memory copy and buffer-related tokens that influence the vulnerable/non-vulnerable decision for a single instance.

(b) CWE-399 (Resource Management) dataset. Local LIME explanation emphasizing resource handling and control-flow tokens that drive the prediction for an individual code sample.

(c) DiverseVul (Multi-type Vulnerabilities) dataset. Local LIME explanation illustrating heterogeneous token contributions arising from mixed vulnerability patterns in a single instance.

Fig. 8. Local LIME explanations for CodeT5 across vulnerability datasets. Highlighted tokens indicate features with the strongest local influence on individual vulnerability detections.

7. Conclusion and future work

This paper presented a Responsible AI-driven framework for software vulnerability detection that operationalizes fairness, interpretability, security, reliability, and transparency within a unified evaluation pipeline. Unlike conventional approaches that emphasize predictive accuracy alone, the proposed framework integrates structured verification mechanisms to assess explanation quality, adversarial resilience, and decision consistency alongside detection performance. The framework was evaluated across multiple deep learning and pre-trained LLMs on three datasets—CWE-119, CWE-399, and DiverseVul. Experimental results show that competitive vulnerability detection performance can be achieved while simultaneously providing interpretable explanations, validating explanation consistency through controlled perturbation, and assessing security under adversarial conditions. Future work will extend the framework to additional programming languages and large-scale repositories to further evaluate generalizability. We also plan to investigate stronger adaptive adversarial scenarios and explore energy-efficient and human-in-the-loop extensions to support sustainable and actionable vulnerability management workflows.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nihala Basheer: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Data curation, Conceptualization. Shareeful Islam: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. Prabhat

(a) CWE-119 (Buffer Overflow) dataset. Masking top-ranked attention tokens leads to a sharp reduction in vulnerability confidence, indicating decision-critical memory-related cues.

(b) CWE-399 (Resource Management Vulnerabilities) dataset. Vulnerability confidence decreases as highly attended resource-handling tokens are progressively masked.

(c) DiverseVul (Multi-type Vulnerabilities) dataset. Occluding top attention-ranked tokens causes a substantial drop in vulnerability confidence, confirming attention faithfulness.

Fig. 9. Attention faithfulness analysis via token occlusion. For representative vulnerable instances, progressively masking tokens ranked by attention rollout, importance leads to a marked reduction in predicted vulnerability probability, indicating that these tokens constitute decision-critical evidence.

Kumar: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. Danish Javeed: Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. Najmul Islam: Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision.

Compliance with ethical standards

This article does not contain any studies with human participants and/or animals performed by any of the authors.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The DiverseVul dataset used in this study is publicly available from the authors' GitHub repository: <https://github.com/wagner-group/diversevul>, with direct download links provided in the repository. The Code Gadget Database (CGD) used to derive CWE-119 and CWE-399 data is available as part of the CGCL project on GitHub: <https://github.com/CGCL-codes/VulDeePecker>. The CWE taxonomy pages referenced for vulnerability definitions are available from the official Common Weakness Enumeration site.

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